

ABSTRACT

AGAPITO, JEAN A., PAPILLERA, MAGDALENA A., DERLA, MOISES JR. O., The Role of Interpersonal Communication in the Sanggunian and Katipunan ng mga Kabataan as Agents for Development of San Antonio, Milaor, Camarines Sur.

(Ateneo de Naga University, March 1998)

This study aims to find out the role of Interpersonal Communication in the youth sector as agent for community development of a particular barangay of the town of Milaor, Camarines Sur. The researchers consider the importance of such kind of communication for they believe that it is more existent within the community than other forms of communication. Likewise, this study gives accent to the role of Sangguniang Kabataan of San Antonio, Milaor, Camarines Sur being given the task to stand out as representative of the youth sector, an independent body to lead their members (KB), to initiate projects and who pledge to serve mankind. Both have the responsibilities to be done, thus considering them one of the agents for community development.

The researchers preferred interview using interview questionnaires and participatory observation as their procedures for data gathering. For the analysis of data, the researchers used the frequency count percentage to determine the general situations of the group.

Through the researchers' interaction with the respondents, it was found out that most of the SK and KB of San Antonio are educated enough, thus they are able to understand interpersonal communication better and recognize its importance as well. The SK council has their programs and activities intended for community development. Yet, they lack funds including the allocation for information dissemination intended for officers and members integration programs. Aside from that mentioned insufficiencies, there are still

existing hindrances not to mention them all. Officers recognized the importance of meetings to encourage members participation. The researchers gave recommendations to the SK officers and members comprising the organization, government and to the future researchers for the improvement of the SK organization with the help of interpersonal communication for the attainment of community development.